

Dynamic model of Thermal Management System for hybrid electric aircraft propulsion system with different coolant investigation

Sofia Caggese¹ and Marco Fioriti²

Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, Politecnico di Torino, C.so Duca degli Abruzzi n.24, Turin, Italy

Flavio Di Fede³

Leonardo Labs, Future Aircraft Technologies, Leonardo S.p.A., c.so Castelfidardo 22, 10138 Turin, Italy

In recent years, in order to achieve environmental sustainability goal, the transport sector, like the major polluting industries, has been moving towards electrification. In aviation, this entails a replacement of the combustion propulsion system. The TMS is the system most affected by this challenge. This paper reports on the development of a model to investigate the performance of the PTTMS for an electric engine, starting with its static dimensioning. This study reports that the system can handle 26 kW. By not meeting the requirements of the heat source, the paper compares different coolants, including the introduction of dispersed nanoparticles in the conventional coolant. The adoption of nanofluids complies with heat source requirements and achieves higher heat transfer efficiencies due to their higher thermal conductivity compared to the base fluid.

I. Nomenclature

bf	= base fluid
C_p	= specific heat, [J/kg/K]
d	= nanoparticle diameter [m]
φ	= volumetric fraction
k	= thermal conductivity, [W/m/K]
K_B	= Boltzmann constant
μ	= dynamic viscosity, [kg/m/s]
nf	= nanofluid
np	= nanoparticle
ρ	= density, [kg/m ³]
Pr	= Prandtl number
Re	= Reynolds number
T	= mean temperature [K]
T_f	= coolant freezing temperature [K]

II. Introduction

Electrification is a potentially sustainable way through which the transport industry is trying to reduce its environmental impact. This transition, which causes combustion engines to be replaced with electrified propulsion

¹ Insert Job Title, Department Name, and AIAA Member Grade (if any) for first author.

² Insert Job Title, Department Name, and AIAA Member Grade (if any) for second author.

³ Insert Job Title, Department Name, and AIAA Member Grade (if any) for third author.

system, is a major challenge for aviation. The electrified propulsion system adopts electric motors, fuel cells and batteries as power sources. They are identified as “low grade” heat sources: higher thermal load than traditional aircraft at lower temperatures. In addition, unlike the conventional combustion engines adopted to date, the produced thermal power is not discarded with the exhausted gases. These sustainable choices have an impact on the Thermal Management System (TMS). To meet this challenge, dynamic simulations are an ideal tool for monitoring, controlling, and optimizing the TMS. In fact, utilizing simulation technologies to integrate the system into the digital twin environment is a crucial point. By creating accurate and real-time digital replicas of physical entities, it plays an important role in decision-making. This paper aims to illustrate the result of a dynamic modelling of the Power Train Thermal Management System (PTTMS), starting from a static sizing model, and to assess the challenges it faces for electrified aviation.

III. PTTMS – On design simulation

On design conditions, the model is the first step of simulation to characterize a design operating point system. The sizing of equipment is obtained thanks to a Python script. The script allows to simulate different fly conditions and replicate several types of aircraft. Design information, parameters, and aircraft size info are contained into an input file, a cpacs file. Table 1 reports the main significant test case information. Similarly, all expected outputs will be collected in a single cpacs output file, some of these are reported in Table 2. The sizing script evaluates, with different levels of accuracy, the equipment of PTTMS. The focus is on the main equipment: the heat exchanger. The aerospace sector, due to weight and volume constraints, prefers the use of compact heat exchangers, characterized by small volumes and increased exchange areas, thanks to lamellar surfaces. The heat exchanger is a crossflow air-to-liquid heat exchanger with a ribbed flat tube as the intercooler surface that allows the exchange between coolant and air. Its sizing requires the inlet and outlet temperatures of the coolant, determined by heat source requirements, coolant type, coolant mass flow rate, and design point. As a result of the developed script, the mass of the PTTMS, mass of the heat exchanger, volume and spatial dimensions, diameter and mass of the pipes, mass of the pump and other physical properties of the PTTMS elements are obtained.

Table 1 Sizing model input

Input		Unit	Value
Mission	altitude	[m]	7260
	Air velocity	[m/s]	40
Environment	Delta ISA	[-]	20
Installation	Heat source position [x;y;z]	[m;m;m]	14.401;5.791;0.789
	Heat exchanger position [x;y;z]	[m;m;m]	13.401;5.791;1.789
PTTMS system	Coolant type	[-]	EG20W80
	Coolant mass flow rate	[kg/s]	0.248
	Max coolant inlet temperature to heat source	[K]	338.15
	Max coolant outlet temperature from heat source	[K]	363.15
	Heat exchanger ID	[-]	11.32
	Heat exchanger AR	[-]	0.342
	Pipe curve number	[-]	4

Table 2 Sizing model output

Output		Unit	Value
Overall PTTMS	Mass	[kg]	4.448
Heat exchanger	Mass	[kg]	1.865
	Volume	[m ³]	0.005390
	Length	[m]	0.380

	Height	[m]	0.120
	Width	[m]	0.118
	Efficiency	[-]	0.361
	Pressure drop	[Pa]	40.32
Pipe	Mass	[kg]	1.134
	Diameter	[m]	0.011
	Length	[m]	4.000
Pump	Mass	[kg]	0.833
	Electric power consumption	[kW]	0.052

IV. PTTMS – Dynamic simulation

Off design conditions model allows to analyze the performance and the behavior of the system. This model's component characteristics are based on the Python script outputs. To ensure communication between the static and the dynamic models, the second model also satisfies the parameterization requirements. The launching of the static model writes an additional output file, a file .gp, containing the required global parameters to update the dynamic model. Furthermore, the sizing script is designed to calculate ad hoc information required by the dynamic simulation.

The analyzed PTTMS is a liquid-air architecture, developed into Simcenter AMESim environment. Simcenter AMESim allows system simulation engineers, thanks to a ready-to-use multi-physics libraries. The model implements thermo-hydraulic, thermal, hydraulic, thermal, and signal libraries to reproduce the physical equipment. Fig. 1 illustrates PTTMS model.

Fig. 1 PTTMS model into AMESim software.

The PTTMS architecture is characterized by a coolant circuit line. In the circuit line module water, a mixture of water and ethylene-glycol or other refrigerants can be used as coolant. The coolant circuit line transports thermal power from the heat source to the heat exchanger. The external environment represents the terminal heat sink, performed by Mission planner tool into AMESim software. It calculates the mission, navigation, and atmosphere properties, defined by International Standard Atmosphere (ISA). A reference mission profile identifies all stages of a traditional flight plan. Fig. 2 summarizes mission characteristics, as rate of climb, flight path angle and Mach number, related to altitude.

Fig. 2 Mission information.

In addition to the mission planner tool, the model has the following constituent elements:

- The overflow tank: used temporarily to store the liquid, thanks to the operation of the pressure cap, which checks the value of circuit pressure, allowing the coolant to be reintegrated again into the main module after the cooldown and the depressurization of the system.
- The expansion tank: used to prevent pressure surges, water hammer and compensates thermal expansion effects due to temperature variation.
- The electric pump: due to a control unit, ensures a desired liquid flow rate and pressure gaps.
- The duct pipes: allow the passage of liquid from one to another equipment.
- The heat source: simulated as a thermal mass.
- The heat exchanger: to exchange heat between two fluids at different temperatures.
- DC Electrical System: a simplified model of electrical connections.
- Control unit: a temperature control loop to regulate pump system torque.

The simulations are taken considering the most similar environment for aerodynamic application. The coolant setup is consistent with the sizing model choices.

V. Results and discussion

A. Coolant setup: EG20W80

Both static and dynamic simulations are conducted under hot day conditions. The reported results are obtained by considering a mixture of 20 % glycol ethylene – 80 % water as coolant. The simulation interval is 13500 seconds in order to include the typical phase of a mission. The purpose is to identify which off-design conditions may have the greatest impact on system performance, in order to modify the power train architecture, redefine the sizing conditions or identify model functional limitations. Consider electric motor and inverter as a heat source is a possible application. This study reports the capability of the system to manage 26 kW, but without complying with the system's own requirements. In fact, although the thermal source is within the operating temperature range, the maximum temperature recorded by the coolant does not meet the requirements. Fig. 3 shows the trend of the inlet and outlet temperature of the coolant, in blue and red respectively, together with the average temperature recorded by the thermal mass, displayed in yellow.

Fig. 3 Dynamic simulation output - Heat source.

1. Post processing and sensitivity analysis for thermal heat flow rate in

A dashboard is developed as a possible postprocessing tool. To make its use interactive, an external command and a time synchronization are introduced. As interacted command is possible to use the thermal power of the heat source. During the simulation, the users can change the thermal power value, introducing the peak of power, and see the effects on the performance. Fig. 4 (a) illustrates an example of an interactive interaction, aimed at replicating any peaks and troughs that might occur during the climbing phases. Due to inertia of thermal mass, there are no visible effects on the measured temperatures, as depicted by Fig. 4 (b).

Fig. 4 Dashboard output – Heat flow rate in (a) and heat source characteristics (b).

Similarly, a sensitivity analysis examines how variation in inputs affect the analyzed complex system. By increasing the heat output, the simulation reports overheating trends and identified size limitations. Fig. 5 (a) depicts five trends of heat source measured temperature: the red line is the test case of this study. Green and pink line report a test case of 17 kW and 13 kW. The system provides fulfilment of requirements in both test case. Blue and yellow line depict two oversizing test case of 39 kW and 52 kW. During cruise phase, the cooling requirements are not met, but neither are the functionality requirements of the electric motor. Fig. 5 (b) portrays the performance of the heat output in relation to what is required to be dissipated (displayed as dotted line). It can be seen how the system is able to converge to what is required but without meeting the cooling specifications.

Fig. 5 Sensitivity analysis output – Heat source temperature comparison (a), Heat flow rate out comparison (b).

For a complete view of the coolant behavior in the cooling circuit, Fig. 6 reproduces the coolant temperatures measured at the inlet and outlet of heat exchanger.

Fig. 6 Sensitivity analysis output – Heat exchanger coolant inlet (a) and outlet (b) temperature comparison.

B. Optimization approach

According to the Model-Based Systems Engineering (MBSE) method, failure to meet the requirements does not allow the system to be validate. MBSE allows for a systematic and traceable approach to system validation, ensuring that the system's design and functionality align with the specified requirements. To identify potential issues and verify that the system's performance aligns with its requirements the following solutions are proposed.

Two approaches can be adopted: re-sizing the heat exchanger or introducing a coolant to facilitate heat exchange. Thanks to dynamic simulation, the sizing conditions of the system are determined which represent new inputs for static simulation. During preliminary aircraft design, an iterative process can be established between static and dynamic models, to identify actual dimensioning set points.

This paper investigates the second approach: innovative coolant is embedded into the model to evaluate the system's behavior under various conditions and scenarios.

1. Coolant simulation campaign

In the second approach a coolant simulation campaign is performed. The first coolant to be introduced is pure water. Although the cooling capacity of the water meets the operational requirements of the heat source, but the pure water can pose significant problem as refrigerant in the aerospace sector. Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 show the comparisons between the two fluids, respectively, the temperature reached by the heat source, and the coolant temperatures at the inlet and outlet of the heat exchanger. The water circuit line model fulfils the heat source requirements, both for cooling and operational specifications.

Fig. 7 Dynamic simulation output – Heat source mean temperature (a) and Heat source heat flow rate (b), Water and EG20W80 comparison.

As Fig. 7 (b) shows, in the case of using water as coolant, the system is able to reach the heat flow to be disposed of earlier than EG20W80 baseline simulation.

Fig. 8 Dynamic simulation output – Heat exchanger coolant inlet (a) and outlet (b) temperature, Water and EG20W80 comparison.

The difficulty of using pure water in aviation leads to investigating other solutions.

Nanofluids have been included in research as potential innovative coolant due to their higher thermal conductivity. Fe_2O_3 is evaluated as nanoparticle in a mixture of 20% ethylene glycol and 80 % water included.

Nanofluid model

In recent years, nanofluid research has attracted interest in industrial applications. Nanofluids are engineered fluids by dispersing nanoparticles in a conventional liquid, such as water, mixture of water and refrigerant, oil. Generally, these solid particles are metallics, oxide ceramics, carbide ceramics, semiconductors, carbon nanotubes, composite materials or a mix of them. Thanks to the thermal conductivity of solid nanoparticles the heat transfer of nanofluids is improve. They are promising for cooling applications. Although the nanoscale should ensure stability of the suspension almost indefinitely, reducing the formation of agglomerates and settling, attention must be paid to the volumetric fraction, the diameter of the nanoparticle, and the method of preparation.

The mathematical resolution of nanofluid model is based on *Nanofluids, Science and technology*, Das [et al.] (Ref. [1]).

Nanofluid density [kg/m^3]:

$$\rho_{nf} = \varphi \rho_{np} + (1 - \varphi) \rho_{bf} \quad (1)$$

where φ represents the volume concentration of nanoparticles and the subscript nf, np and bf refer to the nanofluid, nanoparticle and base fluid.

Nanofluid specific heat [J/kg/K]:

$$c_{p_{nf}} = (\varphi \rho_{nf} c_{p_{np}} + (1 - \varphi) \rho_{bf} c_{p_{bf}}) / \rho_{nf} \quad (2)$$

Nanofluid thermal conductivity [W/m/K]:

$$k_{nf} = k_{bf} \left\{ 1 + 4.4 \left\{ [(2\rho_{bf}K_B T)/(\pi\mu_{bf}^2 d)]^{0.4} P_r^{0.66} \left(\frac{T}{T_f}\right)^{10} \left(\frac{k_{np}}{k_{bf}}\right)^{0.03} \varphi^{0.66} \right\} \right\} \quad (3)$$

where K_B is the Boltzmann constant, T the fluid temperature, T_f the freezing base fluid temperature, P_r the Prandtl number and d the nanoparticle diameter.

Nanofluid dynamic viscosity [kg/m/s]:

$$\mu_{nf} = \mu_{bf}(1 - \varphi)^{2.5} \quad (4)$$

The selected nanoparticle is the Fe_2O_3 with a 1% concentration by volume and a 40 nm diameter. The studied nanofluid is obtained by dispersing 1% of Fe_2O_3 into EG20W80.

Nanofluid model – Results

The improved cooling performance allows to meet functional requirements of the selected heat source. Nanofluid can keep the temperature of the heat source below the desired value. **Error! Reference source not found.** (a) displays the simulation obtained by nanofluid. Both cooling specifications and maximum operative temperature conditions of electric motor are satisfied.

Fig. 9 (b) reports the heat flow rate out comparison between the base coolant, EG20W80, and the innovative one.

Fig. 9 Nanofluid simulation – Heat source output (a) and Heat flow rate output comparison (b).

For a complete view of the behavior of the PTTMS Fig. 10 reports the heat exchanger inlet and outlet temperature of coolant comparison. During the cruise phase, the nanofluid coolant reaches a temperature of 80 °C, below the maximum temperature defined by cooling specifications of the studied electric motor. Similarly, the heat exchanger cools the nanofluid down to 60 °C, below the 65 °C set by the heat source cooling specifications as the maximum inlet temperature, due to the improved thermal efficiency of the heat transfer.

Fig. 10 Nanofluid simulation – Heat exchanger coolant inlet (a) and outlet (b) temperature.

VI. Conclusion

The transition to environmental sustainability is a challenge for TMS. The dynamic simulations analyze PTTMS behavior of an electric-hybrid aircraft. The test case is represented by a thermal power of 26 kW, generated by an electric motor. Cooling is done by air to liquid concept, sized by a parametric Python script. The dynamic model is simulated into Simcenter AMESim environment. The baseline architecture involves ethylene glycol / water mixture, but the heat source requirements are not meet. Several solutions could be evaluated to address the situation: change the overall aircraft design to relax requirements, resize the heat exchanger by identifying the actual design point, investigate other thermal management methods by involving other fluids or different exchanger design. This paper investigates the last approach: innovative coolant is embedded into the model to evaluate the system's behavior under various conditions and scenarios. This study discusses the heat output and the type of coolant, to validate the model according to MBSE method. Coolants include pure water and nanofluids. In the evaluated scenario, H₂O coolant provides the better thermal results, but it is not a typical coolant of aeronautical use. Nanoparticles improve thermal conductivity of the base fluid, meeting the operational and cooling requirements of the heat source.

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